

**CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING APPROACH:
INTRODUCTION AND OVERVIEW**

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***Abstract.** In today's educational world learning English language is being considered one of the most important aspects to pay attention. The first thing in language learning and teaching that comes to our mind is methods, or approaches which maintains easy and right way to acquire knowledge. CLIL is one of useful approaches where students learn a subject and a second language at the same time. A science course, for example, can be taught to students in English and they will not only learn about science, but they will also gain relevant vocabulary and language skills. It's important to note that CLIL is not a means of simplifying content or reteaching something students already know in a new language. CLIL courses should truly integrate the language and content in order to be successful – and success is determined when both the subject matter and language is learned. In this article, I am going to state general information about CLIL and its advantages in foreign language teaching.*

***Key words:** CLIL, approach, simplify, reteaching, acquire.*

Introduction. Content and language integrated learning (CLIL) emerged in the mid-1990s as a product of a European multilingual policy with the original aim of enabling each citizen to use three European languages (L1+ 2 objective) (Council of Europe, 2007). The policy was driven by the necessity to promote economic advances, cooperation within the European Union (EU), and the EU readjustment to migration flows and globalisation (Ruiz de Zarobe, 2017). However, the contemporary practice of integrating content and language learning dates back to bilingual and immersion programmes in the 1960s and 1970s in Canada (Eurydice, 2006; Spanos, 1989) as well as European settings such as the Netherlands, Finland, or Sweden which have usually favoured multilingual education (Hanesová, 2015). According to Mehisto, Marsh, and Frigols (2008), the term CLIL was first coined in 1994, and between 1995 and 2006 it appeared in plans and papers released by the European Commission to promote CLIL as a conducive approach to attain their multilingual policy (e.g., European Commission, 2005; Eurydice, 2006). Initially, it was implemented as micro-experiences in secondary schools in different European countries such as Austria, Italy, and Spain, and it consisted of teaching one or two school subjects, or units within a subject, 2 through an additional language. CLIL provision began as part of mainstream school education or within pilot projects (Eurydice, 2006; Marsh, Maljers, & Hartiala, 2001; Marsh et al., 2009). While the primary aim of CLIL was to encourage citizens to become equipped with an additional language such as a foreign language, heritage or community language (Coyle et al., 2010), it has more recently become a methodology connected to teaching and learning English. This is partly because CLIL has flown its European nest and landed in many different countries globally, where the English is the language most often studied in schools. As Tedick (2020) says, “CLIL programmes have become synonymous with teaching

English in mainland Europe, South America, Asia and elsewhere” (p. xi). As language is a “symbolic resource” (Norton, 2013, p. 49) providing access to higher level education, increased mobility, and ultimately, higher positions in society, it would not be too much to say that CLIL enhances the hegemony of English (Dalton-Puffer, Llinares, Lorenzo, & Nikula, 2014). The issue of which children and teachers have access to CLIL and which do not deserve further research. However, as the chapters in this volume show, the original principles and approaches of CLIL have been locally adapted and new practice models have emerged to ensure they are relevant to their new contexts. While these changes do not diminish the social justice issues with English, they do suggest that CLIL is flexible and adaptable and could potentially make learning and teaching more effective even in resource poor areas. This volume celebrates these new perspectives drawing together recent international research to examine how CLIL supports English language learning globally.

Who is CLIL for?

CLIL can work for students of any age, all the way from primary level to university and beyond. So long as the course content and language aims are designed with the students’ needs in mind, there is no limit as to who can benefit from this teaching approach. However, it is most commonly found in primary and secondary school contexts.

CLIL’s Underlying Principles

Language is learned in context

In CLIL, the subject matter provides the fodder as well as the communicative context in which the target language is learned. That means every vocabulary word, phrase and concept is both immediately relevant and meaningful. There is a direct context in which the word becomes useful, vivid and alive. In a French cooking class, or a Greek philosophy class, the linguistic strides have a base to grow from.

Students learn the words, phrases and concepts as they need them.

In fact, in CLIL, students often first feel the necessity of learning the word/concept before they actually discover what it means. Students might be thinking, “I have no idea what the professor is saying—I don’t even know what tranche means. But I need to learn it if I ever want to make this dish.”

Compare this to a dry vocabulary list, where students first learn the translation of certain words or phrases and then think up scenarios where they can apply them. In many language classes, for example, students might first learn the French expression Allons-y! (Let’s go!) and later think of situations where this could be appropriate. Meanwhile, students in a French cooking class would hear “Allons-y! Allons-y! Allons-y!” as the chef walks around the tables, spurring students to chop, slice and dice faster.

The lessons also include authentic material in the target language. This allows students to hear the language as it is actually spoken and can include written texts and videos such as those found on FluentU online platform.

FluentU takes authentic videos—like music videos, movie trailers, news and inspiring talks—and turns them into personalized language lessons.

And because language is learned in context, students have an easier time saving the lessons in long-term memory. They have a replete of anchors that could remind them. In a way, they have the whole classroom experience tied to it.

In rote memorization, the mental connections are not as strong. The vocabulary given sound so random, even when they’re grouped topically! Sometimes there’s even a disconnect or incongruence for the students, and they begin asking, “Why do we have to learn this? Where am I going to use this?” (Like I said, these questions are automatically answered in a CLIL class. Students see the need to learn it first, before they actually know what a word means.) In the end, context always wins, lasting far longer and stronger than rote memorization.

Language is learned naturally

CLIL not only provides the context for learning, but it does so naturally and in a way that mimics how we learn our first language as kids. It’s important to be reminded that when kindergarten students arrive for the very first day of school, they’re already fluent in their first language. They can communicate with each other, and can tell the teacher what is wrong or what it is they want. This competence was acquired sans any grammar lesson.

In CLIL, there are hardly any grammar lessons. It doesn’t concern itself with surface forms like sentence structure or verb conjugation. Proper observance of rules come far second to the comprehension of language. That’s just how we learned as children. That’s why there are plenty of native speakers who have a hard time explaining the rules of grammar of their native tongue, because they didn’t learn it that way. They acquired their language in the normal course of life, interacting with mom and dad, listening as adults talk to each other, watching cartoons. It was not formalized training; it was a very practical socialization.

A CLIL class offers that same scenario to students—to see language in action, being used to communicate in a concentrated and relevant context. In addition, CLIL understands that in learning any language, errors, guesses and negotiation of meaning are all part of the journey. Although not explicitly stated, mistakes are part of the curriculum.

Language is innately tied to motivation

The importance of motivation in language acquisition has already been established in study after study. What is great about a CLIL class is that it efficiently uses students’ innate motivation for the subject matter (like history, chemistry or math) and indirectly channels it to a target language. Because subject matter and medium of instruction are inseparable and intertwined, the target language ultimately benefits from the natural interest a student has for the topic.

For example, a student who is incredibly interested in the Spanish painter Pablo Picasso might take an entire course about him, in Spanish. Although learning about Picasso is his ultimate driving force, learning the Spanish language becomes a desirable collateral damage to this passion.

What are the challenges of CLIL?

As CLIL is subject-focused, language teachers may also have to develop their own knowledge of new subjects in order to teach effectively. They must also structure classes carefully so that the students understand the content of the lesson, as well as the language through which the information is being conveyed. And when it comes to classroom management, educators need to be very aware of individual student understanding and progress. It’s therefore important to consistently concept check and scaffold the materials to be sure both the language and content are being learned.

How can you apply CLIL to your class?

It's important to have a strategy in place when applying CLIL in your courses. One of the key things to remember is that the language and subject content are given equal weight and that it shouldn't be treated as a language class nor a subject class simply taught in a foreign language.

According to Coyle's 4Cs curriculum (1999), a successful CLIL class should include the following four elements:

- Content – Progression in knowledge, skills and understanding related to specific elements of a defined curriculum;
- Communication – Using language to learn whilst learning to use language;
- Cognition – Developing thinking skills which link concept formation (abstract and concrete), understanding and language;
- Culture – Exposure to alternative perspectives and shared understandings, which deepen awareness of otherness and self.

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